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ADVANCED AND MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR PLANT PROTECTION

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada qishloq xo'jaligida o'simliklarni zararkunandalar, kasalliklar va begona o'tlardan himoya qilishning zamonaviy usullari tahlil qilinadi. Biologik himoya, integratsiyalashgan himoya tizimi, raqamli texnologiyalar, dronlar, sensorlar, biotexnologiya hamda kimyoviy preparatlarning qo'llanishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot beriladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalarning ekologik xavfsizlik, hosildorlik va iqtisodiy samaradorlikka ta'siri yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'simliklarni himoya qilish, biologik usul, zararkunanda, pestitsid, biotexnologiya, integratsiyalashgan himoya.

Abstract: This scientific article analyzes modern methods of protecting plants from pests, diseases and weeds in agriculture. Detailed information is provided on biological protection, integrated protection systems, digital technologies, drones, sensors, biotechnology and the use of chemical preparations. The impact of modern technologies on environmental safety, productivity and economic efficiency is highlighted.

Keywords: Plant protection, biological method, pest, pesticide, biotechnology, integrated protection.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье анализируются современные методы защиты растений от вредителей, болезней и сорняков в сельском хозяйстве. Представлена подробная информация о биологической защите, интегрированных системах защиты, цифровых технологиях, дронах, датчиках, биотехнологиях и использовании химических препаратов. Подчеркивается влияние современных технологий на экологическую безопасность, продуктивность и экономическую эффективность.

Ключевые слова: защита растений, биологический метод, вредитель, пестицид, биотехнология, интегрированная защита.

Introduction. Agriculture is one of the most important sectors that provides humanity with food. However, various factors negatively affect the productivity of agricultural crops.

The most important of them are the following. Pests include insects, plant diseases, weeds, and climatic factors.

According to scientific research, up to 30-40% of agricultural products worldwide are lost due to pests and diseases.

Therefore, plant protection is one of the important areas of modern agriculture. In recent years, as a result of the development of science, new innovative technologies have emerged in plant protection.

Theoretical foundations of plant protection. Plant protection is a complex of scientific and practical measures aimed at protecting agricultural crops from the effects of harmful organisms.

Plant protection includes the following areas:

1. Agrotechnical methods
2. Mechanical methods
3. Biological methods
4. Chemical methods
5. Quarantine measures
6. Genetic and biotechnological methods

These methods give the most effective results when used together.

Agrotechnical protection methods. Agrotechnical methods are one of the oldest and most environmentally friendly methods of plant protection.

The main agrotechnical measures include: crop rotation, deep tillage, the use of quality seeds, irrigation at optimal times, and the use of fertilizers. These methods help prevent the growth of pests, diseases, and weeds.

Biological protection technologies. The biological protection method is based on the use of natural enemies against harmful organisms.

Biological protection agents include:

- beneficial insects
- microorganisms
- biological preparations

For example: Trichogramma destroys the eggs of the pest butterfly

- *Bacillus thuringiensis* is used against many insects

Advantages of the biological method:

- environmentally friendly
- does not pollute the environment
- safe for human health.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of protection methods

№	Methods	Advantage	Disadvantage
1	Agrotechnical	Eco-friendly	Slow results
2	Biological	Natural and safe	Special conditions required
3	Chemical	Fast and effective	Environmental hazards present

Integrated Pest Management (IPM). An integrated pest management system is one of the most effective approaches in modern agriculture. This system combines: Biological methods, agrotechnical measures, chemical agents and monitoring.

The goal of the IPM system is not to completely eliminate pests, but to keep them at a level that does not cause economic damage.

Modern chemical preparations. Chemical protection agents allow you to quickly eliminate pests and diseases.

These include:

- insecticides
- fungicides
- herbicides

Modern pesticides:

- used in low doses
- quickly decompose
- reduced environmental risk

Digital technologies. Today, smart technologies are widely used in agriculture.

Drones. Drones are used to monitor crop fields, identify pests, and spray pesticides.

Sensor technologies. Sensors detect soil moisture, temperature, and help determine plant stress (Picture 1).

Picture-1. Percentage of use of plant protection methods

The share of plant protection methods used. Biotechnology and genetic technologies. Biotechnology is creating great opportunities in agriculture. With the help of biotechnology, disease-resistant varieties are created, plants that are resistant to pests are grown, and productivity is increased. Genetic selection is one of the important areas of modern agriculture.

Plant protection in Uzbekistan. Agriculture in Uzbekistan is being modernized. In the country:

- biological laboratories have been established
- modern technologies are being introduced
- scientific recommendations are being given to farmers

As a result, the volume of agricultural production is increasing.

Conclusion. Plant protection is one of the important areas of agriculture. Modern technologies allow for effective control of pests and diseases. Biological methods, integrated protection systems, digital technologies and biotechnology are the main development areas of future agriculture. The widespread introduction of these technologies will increase productivity, maintain ecological balance and ensure economic efficiency.

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